

777372 - RESOLUTE

Research Empowerment on Solute Carriers

 WP2 – SLC deorphanization
process

D2.1 Signature metabolic profiles using targeted metabolomics

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Abstract

Transporters orchestrate metabolism by regulation of physiological metabolic processes and by rewiring metabolism in disease. However, for many SLCs their function in physiology and disease is unknown. Furthermore, SLCs have mostly been studied individually despite their functional redundancy. This points towards the need to understand the crosstalk between SLCs and metabolism in both an integrated fashion and for individual members. A key component of RESOLUTE's de-orphanization strategy is to generate and analyse high throughput systems biology datasets, making use of the RESOLUTE cell line models comprising SLC knock-out and overexpression cell lines for the entire SLC family. To understand the metabolic phenotypes of individual SLCs as well as functional relationships between SLCs, targeted metabolomics analysis was performed for 358 SLCs, covering 80% of the entire family, upon modulation of SLC expression.

Methods

Cellular models

For the RESOLUTE project, a panel of six human cancer cell lines was chosen which cumulatively cover the expression of about 80% of the SLC family: HCT116, 1321N1, LS180, HuH-7, SK-MEL-28, MDA-MB-468 (with endogenous expression defined as TPM > 1). As an additional model, the isogenic Jump-In T-REx HEK 293 cell line was chosen. The generation of genetically modified cell lines is described in detail in Deliverables D1.2 – D1.5. Relevant cell lines for this deliverable are rescuable KO cell lines in which the deleted SLC can be re-expressed (hereafter referred to as KO-OE cells), described in D1.4, and cell pools expressing individual SLC cDNAs in the Jump-In T-REx HEK 293 cell line (hereafter referred to as WT-OE cells), described in D1.5.

For the targeted metabolomics analysis, the appropriate cell line model for each SLC was chosen based on its expression across the panel of cell lines described above. In case the SLC is endogenously expressed in one of the six cancer cell lines and a respective knockout cell line could be generated, the KO-OE cell line model was chosen for targeted metabolomics analysis. In case the SLC is not endogenously expressed in any of the cancer cell lines or it was not possible to derive a respective knockout cell line, the HEK JumpIn WT-OE model was chosen for targeted metabolomics.

During the selection of appropriate cell lines for each SLC the following quality control parameters were taken into consideration: confirmation of knockout by Sanger sequencing, confirmation of cDNA expression by RNA-sequencing, protein expression by western blot, localization by immunofluorescence in combination with organelle markers.

Metabolite extraction

Cells were plated in 6-well or 24-well plates in culture medium in the absence or presence of 1 µg/ml doxycycline and grown at 37°C and 5% CO₂ (150 000 cells per well for HCT-116 and LS180, 100 000 cells per well for 1321N1, 50 000 cells per well for HuH7, 70 000 cells per well for SKMEL, 750 000 / 150 000 cells per well in poly-L-lysine coated 6-well / 24-well plates for HEK293). After 16-24 h, cells were first gently washed with room temperature bicarbonate buffer (91 mM NH₄HCO₃, pH 7.4). Then, cells were transferred to ice where 300 µl/well in 24-well plate or 1500 µl/well in 6-well plate) of ice-cold 80:20 MeOH:H₂O containing a mixture of isotopically labelled internal standards [Synthetic heavy isotope labelled metabolites from Sigma and Cambridge Isotope Labs as well as Metabolite Yeast Extract (U-13C, 98%) from ISOtopic Solutions, Vienna, Austria] was added to each well. The cells were then scraped and transferred to a pre-cooled Eppendorf tube and immediately snap frozen in liquid nitrogen. Samples were thawed on ice before being centrifuged at 16,000 × g for 10 min at 4°C. The clarified metabolite-containing supernatants were moved into a high-performance liquid chromatography vial and stored at –80°C until further preparation for LC-MS/MS analysis.

Mass spectrometric analysis

Cell extracts were dried using a nitrogen evaporator. The dry residue was reconstituted in 16 µl H₂O and 4 µl of sample extract was used for LC-MS/MS analysis. A 1290 Infinity II UHPLC system (Agilent Technologies) coupled to a 6470 triple quadrupole mass spectrometer (Agilent Technologies) was used for the LC-MS/MS analysis. The chromatographic separation was carried out on a ZORBAX RRHD Extend-C18, 2.1 × 150 mm, 1.8 µm analytical column (Agilent Technologies). The column was maintained at a temperature of 40°C. The

mobile phase A was 3% MeOH (v/v), 10 mM tributylamine, 15 mM acetic acid in H₂O, and mobile phase B was 10 mM tributylamine, 15 mM acetic acid in MeOH. The gradient elution with a flow rate 0.25 mL/min was performed for a total time of 24 min followed by back flushing of the column using a 6 port 2-position divert valve for 8 min using acetonitrile. At the end of the run 8 min of column equilibration with 100% mobile phase A was performed. The triple quadrupole mass spectrometer was operated in electrospray ionization negative mode, spray voltage 2 kV, gas temperature 150°C, gas flow 1.3 L/min, nebulizer 45 psi, sheath gas temperature 325°C, and sheath gas flow 12 L/min. The metabolites of interest were detected using a dynamic Multiple Reaction Monitoring (MRM) mode.

Data processing

During initial data analysis, MassHunter 10.0 software (Agilent Technologies) was used to establish correct identification and integration of mass spectrometric signals for each queried metabolite and the corresponding internal standard. Absolute quantification is based on ten-point linear calibration curves with internal standardization. To calculate metabolite concentrations from the raw LC-MS data, a novel software was implemented (publication in preparation). Briefly summarized, it is based on a convolutional neural network (CNN) that reports a peak type (chromatographic peak or background) as well as the chromatographic peak borders (only for reported chromatographic peaks). The model was trained on an LC-MS batch (R100140) processed with MassHunter 10.0 software that was evaluated by a human expert for the presence or absence of chromatographic peaks as well as manually integrated chromatographic peaks. Different model architectures (e.g., number of hidden layers, number of convolutions), meta-parameters and augmentation procedures were implemented and compared before settling on a CNN that consisted of 4 hidden layers. A second, independent dataset obtained with the same analytical method but from a different batch (R100138) was used to validate the generated model's performance. There, the model achieved a high accuracy of recognizing chromatographic peaks (more than 97.5% of chromatographic peaks are correctly reported and around 12.5% of background signals are incorrectly considered to be chromatographic peaks) and appropriate peak integration boundaries (more than 95% peak overlap weighted by the area). Peak or background area integration was carried out between the peak boundaries established by linear interpolation between successive scans multiplied by the retention time difference of these scans. Any constant offset in the respective extracted ion current (EIC) area (i.e., minimum signal value present in each scan of an integration area) was accounted for.

The remaining datasets not used for generating and validating the above-described machine learning model were processed with this optimized model resulting in predictions. All these were carefully examined and if the human supervisor disagreed with the model's prediction, the manual curation replaced the automated prediction (i.e., chromatographic peak or background, peak borders). Any EIC without a chromatographic peak was regarded as noise, which was likewise integrated to offer replacement values for missing data. This integration of noise was performed on the average peak width (from the 25% to the 75% percentile) of all samples of a particular substance and batch that contained detectable chromatographic peaks. Internal standard ratios were calculated by dividing the peak areas of the substance and the respective internal standard. Then, on defined calibration samples a linear calibration curve weighted by the inverse of the expected concentrations was established. Outliers in the calibration curve were manually eliminated and not used in the final regression curve. The major features of the identified peaks or background regions, the type of quantifier (either peak area or internal standard ratio), and the final component concentrations in the sample were compiled into a data matrix for further statistical analysis.

Statistical analysis

Differential abundance analysis and visualization of the results

Quantified metabolite concentrations are statistically contrasted between doxycycline induced and uninduced samples to identify differentially abundant metabolites upon overexpression of a transporter. The contrast of doxycycline induced to uninduced samples is performed for each cell line individually. P-values are calculated from a regression analysis after fitting a model with doxycycline treatment as explanatory variable for the analysis of the WT-OE cell lines (metabolite concentration ~ Doxycycline treatment), and a model with doxycycline treatment and clone as explanatory variables for the analysis of the KO-OE cell lines with at least 2 profiled clones (metabolite concentration ~ Doxycycline treatment + clone). To decrease the false discovery

rate, p-values are corrected for multiple testing using the Benjamini-Hochberg correction. To ensure separation of the samples by treatment (doxycycline induction) a Principal component analysis (PCA) is performed and its score plot for each cell line is illustrated (Figure 1.A). Upon differential abundance analysis, the metabolic profile of each individual cell line is visualized through boxplots of metabolite concentrations before and after doxycycline treatment (Figure 1.B) as well as volcano plots showing the differentially regulated metabolites upon overexpression of an SLC (Figure 1.C).

Figure 1. Visualizations performed for each cell line. A. Principal component analysis (PCA) shows separation of the samples of each cell line according to doxycycline treatment. B. Boxplots show levels of metabolite concentrations in doxycycline induced and uninduced samples of a cell line (only 20/200 metabolites shown in this example). C. Differentially regulated metabolites (up-regulated metabolites shown in red and down-regulated metabolites shown in green) upon overexpression of an SLC are shown in a volcano plot (x-axis shows the log₂ fold change of a metabolite upon doxycycline induction and y-axis shows the adjusted p-value obtained from the differential analysis; vertical lines show the cut-offs used for the adjusted p-value (<0.05) and the log₂ fold change value (absolute log₂ fold change > 0.5)).

Clustering SLCs by profile similarity

In addition, the metabolic profiles of all cell lines with genetic modification of individual SLCs are clustered according to profile similarity. Euclidean distance is used as similarity metric and similarity between profiles is calculated from the z-scores computed on the log₂ fold change between induced and uninduced samples. Cell line and metabolite clusters are then detected based on the Euclidean distance matrix of the cell lines. The optimal number of clusters identified in the data is computed via the gap statistic (i.e., goodness of clustering measure). Independent clusters are further studied by performing pathway enrichment analysis on the metabolite groups and by annotating SLC features such as annotated localization, SLC family, coupled ions or annotated substrate class. In general, clustering SLC metabolic profiles by similarity allows us on one hand to study the functional relationships between SLCs and on the other hand to gain insights for orphan SLCs by deriving hypotheses about their function through the annotated SLCs of the same cluster.

Results

Overview of targeted metabolomics analysis of SLC family

Targeted metabolomics as described above has been performed for 358 SLCs (all 3 steps of the pipeline shown in Figure 2.A are completed). Of these 358 SLCs, 185 SLCs were screened in a HEK model where the SLC was overexpressed in WT cells while 173 SLCs were screened in a KO-overexpression (Figure 2.C). (Figure 2.B). Most of the SLC families are well represented as shown in Figure 2.B. For 60 out of 70 families more than 50% of their members were profiled (with 29/60 families reaching a coverage of 100%). For 3 families the coverage ranges between 25-40% while only 7 families (mostly single member families) are not covered at all (CLN3: 1 member, SLC32: 1 member, SLC41: 3 members, SLC48: 1 member, SLC53: 1 member, SLC64: 1 member, TMEM104: 1 member).

In the differential metabolite analysis, significantly deregulated metabolites (adjusted p-value <0.05) were found in 90% of the SLCs screened in a KO-OE model and in 70% of the SLCs screened in a WT-OE model. This discrepancy can be attributed to the difference in the statistical model used for data analysis (WT-OE: metabolite concentration ~ Doxycycline treatment vs KO-OE: metabolite concentration ~ Doxycycline treatment + clone).

Figure 2. Overview of the targeted metabolomics data generation/analysis. A. The 3 main steps of data analysis after quantification using mass spectrometry. B. SLC family coverage after completion of the targeted metabolomics experiment. Most of the SLC families are covered by more than 50%. C. Number of SLCs screened in the different cell line models in the targeted metabolomics experiment.

Robustness of metabolite quantification method

Metabolite identification and absolute quantification are among the most reliable methods for comparative metabolomics approaches and to account for analytical batch-effects. The here presented dataset consisted of 358 different SLCs and could therefore not be analyzed in a single, continuous batch, but was split up in more than 70 different sub-batches each of which was individually measured in a course of 3 years. Consequently, many intentional but likewise unintentional alternations to the LC-MS system have occurred, which introduce a high inter-batch bias. Especially when SLCs from different batches are to be compared, this is problematic and needs to be accounted for. To investigate the qualitative and quantitative reproducibility of the analytical measurements as well as the extend of the analytical bias of the presented dataset, several tests were carried out, which are summarized in the following subsections.

Calibration samples

Calibration samples were used to derive absolute compound concentrations from peak areas with and without correction of matrix effects by internal standards. The calibration samples were measured as single replicates in each analytical batch.

Using the peak areas of the substances detected in the calibration samples (levels 1 to 9 were used), histograms of relative standard deviation (RSD) per calibration level were generated (Figure 3.A). Median RSD values were around 60% and for the 90%-percentile RSD values were around 110%. Furthermore, the two calibration levels with the lowest compound concentrations showed even higher values. Also, these calibration samples show a slight separation in a multivariate PCA scores plot (Figure 3.C).

Subsequently, a linear n-point calibration curve manually optimized was applied for each substance and measurement batch individually. Of the more than 14,000 calibration curves established, the majority (more than 92%) had R² values above 0.75 and used at least 4 or more of the different calibration levels indicating that for most of the substances a good linear fit was achieved and that a wide dynamic range was covered (Figure 4). Consequently, the RSD and PCA analysis of the calibration samples was repeated using these concentration values rather than the peak area (Figure 3 B and D). The median RSD value per calibration level has considerably decreased for levels 3 to 9 (on average by a factor of more than 50%), but for calibration levels 1 and 2 no or only feeble improvement could be observed. Furthermore, also the 90% percentile showed reduced values for the calibration levels 4 to 8. However, looking at the PCA scores plot after calibrating the samples and calculating the absolute concentrations, a separation of the different levels is still obvious when accounting for the concentration differences (division by expected concentration). This partial separation is likely due to the fact that the linear interpolation of the calibration samples does not sufficiently compensate for non-linear effects and/or other batch-related effects/differences. Nevertheless, in summary the absolute concentration using the calibration samples improves the comparability of different samples across the measurement batches of the presented dataset. Also, at the same time it allows to elegantly account for a large amount of the batch effects such as signal increase/decrease thereby making inter-batch comparisons possible.

NIST and RESOLUTE QC samples

The presented dataset included quality control samples obtained from NIST frozen serum standard (<https://www-s.nist.gov/srmors/certificates/1950.pdf>). These samples were measured as three biological and multiple technical replicates in each of the different batches. The intra-batch measurement accuracy for individual substances was high with median relative standard deviations across the NIST replicates was 25% or less and the 90% percentile was 70% or less regardless of the quantifier type (peak area, internal standard ratio, or absolute concentration, Figure 5.A-C). When looking at the individual substances aggregated by the different batches, higher RSD values can be observed for both the median as well as the 90% percentile (Figure 5 D-F). This is of no surprise as this aggregation also contains a lot of the technical variation from the batches. When the peak areas are considered, the RSD values of these NIST samples aggregated by the measurement batches are similar to those of the calibration samples for absolute quantification (Figure 3.A and Figure 5.D). However, when the internal standard or absolute quantification are used for matrix effect correction or even after absolute quantification, the decrease of the median and 90% percentile can no longer be observed for these NIST samples. On the contrary, these two location parameters of the RSD distributions have higher values with the median at around 90% RSD and the 90% percentile at 250%, which corresponds to an increase by a factor of 5 to 7. Interestingly in a PCA scores plot the clustering of the replicates and measurement batches seems to have improved (Figure 7).

A second set of quality control samples, namely the RESOLUTE QC samples, confirm this trend and the increase of RSD values when all samples are aggregated by substance. Similar median values are observed here, but lower 90% percentiles are present (Figure 6). Furthermore, a slight improvement in the clustering after absolute quantification in the scores plot of a PCA can be observed as well (Figure 8).

Figure 3. A and B: Overview of relative standard deviation of individual substances aggregated over all measurement batches. C and D: PCA scores plots of the different calibration levels. Each dot is a calibration sample in a particular measurement sequence. A and C: Peak areas were used as quantifier values. B and D: Concentration values after regression calculation using the same calibration samples were used.

A Overview of regression lines

774 (5.3%) features have an R2 below 0.75, 487 (3.4%) features use less than 4 points, and 1148 (7.9%) features fulfill at least one of the criteria (red points). In total, 14525 points are shown

B

Calibration points	Count	95-Percentile	90-P	80-P	Median	% greater 0.9	% greater 0.95
2	128	-0.111	-0.015	0.542	1.000	68.8	67.2
3	359	0.191	0.489	0.692	0.943	58.5	46.5
4	657	0.342	0.657	0.800	0.945	64.4	47.0
5	968	0.556	0.756	0.866	0.961	72.3	56.5
6	2390	0.782	0.837	0.900	0.970	80.0	62.4
7	4383	0.801	0.850	0.910	0.980	82.2	69.5
8	2808	0.800	0.859	0.922	0.981	84.5	71.2
9	2339	0.435	0.787	0.881	0.984	77.2	67.7
10	493	0.918	0.961	0.987	0.998	96.1	92.1

Figure 4. Overview of R2 values and points used for establishing linear, weighted (1/expected concentration) calibration curves. A: Each dot represents an individual substance in a separate measurement batch of the presented dataset. B: Overview of location parameters for the linear models aggregated by the number of calibration points used.

Figure 5. Relative standard deviations of NIST samples. A – C: grouped by substance and measurement batch, D – F: grouped by substances and aggregated across measurement batches, A and D: peak areas, B and E: ISTD ratios, C and F: absolute concentration values.

Figure 6. Relative standard deviations of RESOLUTE QC samples. A – C: grouped by substance and measurement batch, D – F: grouped by substances and aggregated across measurement batches, A and D: peak areas, B and E: ISTD ratios, C and F: absolute concentration values.

Figure 7. PCA scores plot of the NIST samples in the different measurement batches. A: peak areas, B: absolute concentration values.

Figure 8. PCA scores plot of the RESOLUTE QC samples in the different measurement batches. A: peak areas, B: absolute concentration values.

Comparability of samples from different batches

The comparison of the calibration and NIST/RESOLUTE QC samples across the batches showed contradictory results. For the calibration samples an improvement of the comparison could be observed (lower RSD values after absolute quantification in comparison to calibration with peak areas) and excellent RSD values (median of around 20%) were achieved throughout all batches, while the comparison of the NIST and RESOLUTE QC samples was reduced (higher RSD values after absolute quantification in comparison to peak areas). Ideally both types would have shown an improvement. Nevertheless, the median and 90% percentile location parameters of the RSD distributions indicate a high reproducibility of the substances' concentration even across the different measurement batches, which is about 6 times as high as the inter-batch reproducibility (Figure 5.C and F).

In an experiment consisting of 80 measurement batches, it can be expected that not all analytical sources of random and/or systematic variation can be easily accounted for. In the here presented dataset, it can be concluded that due to the high number of samples, which made it necessary to measure them in many different batches, certainly such bias was introduced. However, for any interpretation based on samples from different batches, care should be taken to not mistake systematic batch effects and differences for biological ones. Thus, batch-correction should ideally be carried out before. On the other hand, for any samples within a certain batch the analysis indicates a high analytical precision and accurate quantification of the results.

Biological interpretation and validation of results

Results from the analysis for differential abundance of metabolites in individual SLCs as well as from the similarity clustering are further investigated by comparison to existing literature. Hypotheses around novel metabolic functions of SLCs will be validated with additional experiments. The described data and outcome of further analyses will be published in a peer-reviewed article.

In order to share the data with the scientific community a data release workshop will take place in October 2022.

Discussion

In order to achieve the level of required throughput within the given time and resources, we adapted the methodology as described in the Description of Action in two points. First, we implemented an in-house mass spectrometry method as described above instead of using a commercial kit. Second, we implemented an improved data processing workflow to minimize the time required for manual curation.

Novel quantitative method

After initially testing the application of a commercial kit for metabolite quantification, we developed an in-house metabolomics method utilizing reversed phase ion pairing chromatography and absolute quantification based on heavy isotope labelled internal standards and external calibration curves. The development of a customized analytical method allowed for more flexibility regarding the metabolite panel. While the commercial kit was focused on a very limited number of hydrophilic metabolites including mainly amino acids and bioactive amines (around 40 in total), 40 acyl-carnitines and around 100 lipids, the customized in-house analytical method now quantifies around 200 hydrophilic metabolites of which more than 140 can robustly be quantified in the RESOLUTE cell lines, covering more than 50 diverse metabolic pathways as illustrated in Figure 9. Application of a very robust liquid chromatography system based on ion pairing reversed phase column technology allowed for outstanding reproducibility regarding retention times both within batches and between batches. Low variation in retention times of the LC-MS analysis helped in the establishment of ML-based automation of data processing. Use of an in-house analytical method also allowed for more flexibility regarding downstream data processing. The use of the more economical solution of an in-house analytical method allowed to repurpose funds that would have been spent on expensive but suboptimal commercial kits to be invested in the establishment of customized analytical technology that was optimised for the needs of the targeted metabolomics work package within the RESOLUTE consortium.

Figure 9. KEGG pathway coverage of detected metabolites across different cellular models (HEK293 and HCT-116 cell lines) with SLC overexpression in WT or SLC KO background). Red points indicate individual metabolites.

Improved data processing workflow

Humans have an extraordinary system for recognizing visual information such as chromatographic peaks in LC-MS data. Unfortunately, they are slow when this task needs to be carried out several times. Furthermore, it also bears the risk of person-to-person and day-to-day variation as it is a time- and labour-intensive task. An algorithm-based quantification is therefore preferable for large-scale experiments with multiple batches and thousands of samples. The newly established data processing workflow therefore enabled several improvements: Peak integration is based only on the EIC and uses the same rules for each peak based on the ML-based algorithm and the generated model derived from the training set. This leads to more consistency between batches. Moreover, the new ML-based data processing method also reduces data missingness as illustrated in Figure 10. In cases where true signals can only be detected in a subset of samples, background noise is integrated in the samples with signals below the limit of detection. Integration follows the peak boundaries that can be observed in samples with true signals. As a result, data imputation of missing values can also use this noise values rather than to impute with LOD values or values based on other strategies. Reduced missingness also helps to increase data points for multi-variate statistical analysis in overall SLC comparisons. Finally, automated peak integration is also much faster than manual integration. Together with a manual verification and integrity check it saved many resources during the generation of this dataset.

Figure 10. Data missingness improved after PeakBot peak integration. Missingness in 124 metabolites out of 184 detected in total in both integration methods is visualized (these 124 are metabolites showing missingness after manual integration). From 52 metabolites that showed >50% missingness in more than 2000 samples after manual integration, the number dropped to only 5 metabolites with >50% missingness after PeakBot integration.

Conclusion

We successfully obtained metabolic profiles using targeted metabolomics for >80% of the SLC family, using a robust quantitative mass spectrometry method and standardized workflow. This data set allows the exploration of metabolic consequences upon SLC expression and creates hypotheses for novel SLC substrates and functional relationships in subgroups of SLCs.

Repository for primary data

A data release workshop will take place in October 2022 for reviewing the data sets. After the workshop, a data release proposal will be shared with the consortium to enable public release of the data. Following the approval of the data release by the consortium, the raw data will be deposited at MetaboLights (<https://www.ebi.ac.uk/metabolights/>). In addition, a RESOLUTE dashboard for visualization and exploration of data sets will be implemented in the RESOLUTE web page (<https://re-solute.eu/resources/dashboards>).